

A New View of Consciousness: Understanding It as a Pattern Recognition Signal of the Brain

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Abstract

This paper presents a new framework for understanding consciousness as a pattern recognition signal of the brain. The author's expert system is considered a highly reliable model for intuition, given the significant number of their statistically significant coincidences. Intuition is thought to be a combinatorial coding elimination algorithm for pattern recognition used by the brain. Pattern recognition is a fundamental cognitive process that allows both biological organisms and machines to identify patterns in data and make predictions based on those patterns. In the case of machines, pattern recognition is a key component of many artificial intelligence systems, including computer vision, speech recognition, and natural language processing. Combinatorial codes refer to the idea that individual neurons in the brain may represent a specific combination of features or concepts, rather than just one specific feature or concept. Recent research has suggested that combinatorial codes may be used in various areas of the brain involved in pattern recognition, such as the visual cortex and the hippocampus. This model suggests that consciousness arises from the integration of pattern recognition signals across various regions of the brain, which allows for the generation of coherent perceptual experiences and the ability to make flexible and adaptive decisions. The paper proposes that consciousness represents the signals within a brain that uses intuition as a pattern recognition algorithm on combinatorial codes for pattern recognition.

Introduction

This paper presents a new framework for understanding consciousness as a pattern recognition signal of the brain. Pattern recognition (Kulikowski, 1991) is a fundamental cognitive process that allows both biological organisms and machines to identify patterns in data and make predictions based on those patterns. It involves identifying patterns in various forms of data, such as images, sounds, or language, and using those patterns to make decisions or predictions. While pattern recognition algorithms typically involve the use of statistical or machine learning techniques, recent research suggests that combinatorial codes (Lovász, 1979) may also play a crucial role. In the case of machines, pattern recognition is a key component of many artificial intelligence systems, including computer vision, speech recognition, and natural language processing. Pattern recognition algorithms typically involve the use of statistical or machine learning techniques to identify patterns in data and make predictions based on those patterns. While pattern recognition algorithms typically involve the use of statistical or machine learning techniques, (Bishop, 1995) it is argued that combinatorial codes may play a crucial role in pattern recognition by the brain.

In the case of biological organisms like humans, pattern recognition is a fundamental cognitive process that allows us to recognize objects, faces, and speech sounds, among other things. The paper suggests that the similarity of an expert system, developed by the author, to human intuition (Thomas, 2023) carries a statistically overwhelming number of coincidences. The expert system for diagnosing 225 eye diseases uses an elimination algorithm that acts on global data and avoids asking stupid questions, similar to the awareness of the mind to the whole information. Like human intuition, the expert system can identify objects without seeking exact matches and can operate in any field. By instantly recognizing events having unique information, the expert system resembles intuition. The paper suggests that the brain applies the intuition algorithm on combinatorial codes. Combinatorial codes refer to the idea that individual neurons in the brain may represent (Szyszka P, 2012) a specific combination of features or concepts, rather than just one specific feature or concept. Recent research has suggested that combinatorial codes may be used in various areas of the brain involved in pattern recognition, such as the visual cortex and the hippocampus. For example, studies have shown that individual neurons in the visual cortex can respond selectively to specific combinations of visual features, such as orientation and color. Individual neurons in the brain may

represent a specific combination of features or concepts, rather than just one specific feature or concept. For example, a neuron may fire when a person sees a face with a particular combination of facial features, (Deen, Ben, 2017) such as a specific nose shape and eye color. Recent research has suggested that combinatorial codes may be used in various areas of the brain involved in pattern recognition, such as the visual cortex (Rosa, M.G.P. 2002) and the hippocampus. This model suggests that consciousness arises from the integration of pattern recognition signals across various regions of the brain, which allows for the generation of coherent perceptual experiences and the ability to make flexible and adaptive decisions. As such, this paper presents a new framework for understanding consciousness as a pattern recognition signal, drawing on insights from neuroscience, psychology, and computer science. The paper proposes that the concept of intuition as a pattern recognition algorithm and the view of the mind as a pattern recognition entity, in which consciousness represents the signals within a brain that recognizes patterns.

LLMs Are Pattern Recognition Entities

With large language models, the multitude of relationships between texts in a vast database constitutes a vast combinatorial memory of relationships. This memory resembles the brain, which discovers patterns in vast combinatorial memories in axon hillocks. (Palay SL, 1968) The weight of a node in a neural network is typically represented as a set of matrices, with each matrix representing the strength of the connection between two nodes. During training, the weights change between negative and positive values through back-propagation to achieve the desired results. The intelligence and memory of the network are precisely calibrated by the weights, which use floating-point numbers, giving a wide range and precision to each number. A 32-bit floating-point number can represent 10 million distinct values, and systems can use 128-bit numbers also. So each node in the system can precisely represent and remember an infinite number of alternative patterns. The output of a neural network (Zorzi M, 2013) can precisely measure an image as belonging to exactly one item of an infinite number of image categories. It might be a vector of probabilities that represent (Chicco D, 2020)the likelihood of the input image belonging to each possible category. In natural language processing, the output of a neural network might be a vector of embeddings that represent the meaning of a sentence or a word. The meaning of the message or the understanding derived from the output of a neural network depends on the specific application and context of the network. The output can be interpreted as a probability distribution over a set of possible outputs, or as representing a continuous value. The interpretation of the output vector depends on the specific application and the nature of the problem being solved. In some cases, additional post-processing or interpretation may be required to derive a meaningful understanding or decision from the output of the network. In summary, the combinatorial memory of large language models resembles the brain's memory, and the weights of the neural network precisely calibrate the intelligence and memory of the system. The output of a neural network is a numerical representation of the predictions or decisions made by the network based on the input data and can be interpreted differently based on the specific application and context of the network.

Expert-AI - A New Expert System

Expert-AI is a tool (Thomas, 2023) designed to diagnose Eye Diseases. It evaluates 225 Eye Diseases and 36 questions to deliver logical answers to the users. In 1990, the ES was presented to a panel of doctors at Vijaya Eye Foundation in Chennai, which treats over 30,000 patients annually. After receiving about 6 responses from the panel to the presented questions, the ES responded with "The Likely Disease Is Angular Conjunctivitis." The doctors were impressed by the ES, which did not ask any "stupid questions" and was faster and more efficient than traditional expert systems. Expert-AI is a tool that leverages a publicly available database of diseases to diagnose a patient's condition based on their reported symptoms. The system stores the relationships between symptoms and diseases and eliminates any diseases that have no connections to the reported symptoms. If a disease has links to all of the symptoms, it is considered the diagnosis. If not, Expert-AI reports that the symptoms do not match any known disease in its database. The frames within the system suggest treatments for the diagnosed disease.

Expert-AI operates on the entire database, making use of general questions to eliminate the possibility of a disease. For instance, 36 questions between them can logically eliminate all 225 eye diseases. If the reported symptoms do not match any of the remaining diseases, Expert-AI reports that it cannot determine a diagnosis. The user of Expert-AI is presented with a sequence of questions with 3 ("Yes" (Y), "Maybe" (U), or "No" (N)) possible response buttons. Y means a positive link - the symptom is always present in the disease. U means the symptom is sometimes present. And N means the symptom is absent for the disease.

After each answer to a presented symptom question, the Expert-AI tests the Y/U/N relationships of all diseases in a single step, in manner similar to the way all cells in a spreadsheet are instantly recalculated.

The Y/U/N relationships are entered specifically for their negative impact. An "Yes" answer eliminates all "N" diseases. If the problem is unilateral, all bilateral eye diseases are eliminated. A "No" answer eliminates all "Y" diseases. If visual acuity is not affected, all eye diseases which impact on visual acuity are eliminated. The Expert-AI also purges questions which have "Y" relationships only to eliminated diseases. The questioning process begins with the question which has the maximum number of "Y" relationships. It ends when the presented symptoms eliminate all but a single disease. Specific questions can then confirm the diagnosis. If all diseases are eliminated, the conclusion is that the presented symptoms do not match any disease in the database. For Expert-AI, it is an unknown disease.

Statistically Compelling Evidence of Resemblance to Intuition

With all relationships in memory, Expert-AI is able to recognize a specific condition instantly. If only one disease has a positive relationship with a unique symptom, a "Yes" response to this symptom eliminates all other diseases, leading to immediate recognition. With his intuition, a doctor may walk into a surgery and instantly identify a heart attack in a patient with just minimal visual cues, recognizing a single pattern among many others in a fraction of a second. This suggests that intuition may be using an elimination algorithm. Expert-AI eliminates the occurrence of "stupid questions" by implementing a more efficient and holistic approach to search. Unlike traditional search algorithms (Uddin S, 2019) that look for a single disease to match a symptom, Expert-AI evaluates the entire database in relation to the current answer. This enables Expert-AI to effectively eliminate any possibilities that have been ruled out by previous answers. Intuition also avoids stupid questions. If a person who believed that all birds fly, encountered an ostrich, he would never again ask whether there are any birds that do not fly. The power of intuition lies in its ability to control the mind through inhibition. (Kuffler SW, 1955) While Expert-AI may follow a logical deductive reasoning approach, intuition also engages in a logical deduction process that cuts off the database when emotions strike. Emotions act as a filter, inhibiting memories that do not align with their specific objectives. For example, when anger strikes, (Otterpohl N, 2022) a person cannot remember reasons why they should not be angry, as those memories are inhibited. Similarly, intuition inhibits irrelevant data, allowing one to focus on the most important and pertinent information.

Even in the animal kingdom, intuition controls behavior through inhibition. When an animal is thirsty and chooses to drink, its hunger pangs are inhibited, enabling the animal to focus solely on satisfying its thirst. Therefore, intuition's strength lies in its ability to selectively inhibit irrelevant information and prioritize the most critical data for decision-making. According to this paper, the nervous system employs a combinatorial recognition model instead of the conventional linear summation model. (Uddin S, 2021) Unlike the linear summation model, which is confined to simple input summation, combinatorial recognition enables the autonomous storage of complex patterns and interconnections between inputs. This approach allows all regions of the nervous system to communicate with one another, addressing the challenge of internal representation for the mind. In addition, intuition plays a critical role in holistically controlling the system. It operates as an elimination algorithm, effectively removing irrelevant information from the entire database. This suggests that intuition functions as an integral component of the combinatorial recognition model, enabling the nervous system to efficiently process and store complex information. Similar to Expert-AI, intuition avoids the limitations of exact pattern recognition by utilizing an elimination algorithm. Many AI algorithms depend on matching the attributes of a known pattern (Zheng L. 2022) with those of a new pattern, stored in computer memory for later retrieval. However, in cases such as face recognition this method of identification becomes increasingly difficult due to the billions of faces in the world, each with thousands of overlapping features that exist on an almost infinite scale.

Expert-AI addresses this challenge by using an elimination algorithm that can establish the identity of a pattern based on its distinctive characteristics. Likewise, intuition employs an elimination algorithm to overcome the challenge of exact pattern recognition, enabling it to filter out irrelevant information and focus on the most important and unique attributes of a given pattern. In doing so, intuition can effectively recognize and identify complex patterns, much like Expert-AI's algorithms. Intuition tackles uncertainty (Hughes C. 1989) through an elimination algorithm, much like Expert-AI. One of the significant challenges in traditional AI is managing uncertainty. Binary logic, which operates on the premise of a characteristic being either present or absent, often struggles to cope with the ambiguous and uncertain relationships

between characteristics and patterns. Fuzzy logic (Thukral S, 2018) addresses this uncertainty by assigning degrees or grades to characteristics, such as short, medium height, tall, and very tall. However, fuzzy logic fails to handle scenarios where a person occasionally wears glasses.

Expert-AI's approach to uncertainty involves eliminating obvious objects and retaining uncertain ones, then using a series of questions to progressively eliminate the remaining possibilities. Similarly, intuition manages uncertainty by applying an elimination algorithm that removes irrelevant information and prioritizes the most significant and relevant attributes of a given pattern. This allows intuition to effectively navigate uncertain situations and make sound decisions in the face of ambiguity, much like Expert-AI's algorithms. Intuition, much like Expert-AI, leverages an elimination algorithm to manage the challenge of context in AI. Identifying context is a significant obstacle for AI researchers, particularly in tasks such as machine translation. Unlike machines, which must systematically compare the characteristics of objects with those stored in memory, the mind instantly recognizes the context of objects or events, drawing on a lifetime of memories and associations. To help address this issue, AI researchers have developed heuristics (Blumenthal-Barby JS, 2015) a method for determining the direction of the search in small search spaces. However, heuristics can only provide limited guidance and can quickly be overwhelmed in large and complex search spaces, leading to the problem of combinatorial explosion. Expert-AI handles the challenge of identifying context (Willis CD, 2016) by using an elimination algorithm that removes irrelevant information and retains uncertain objects, allowing it to deal with the entire database and preserve context in the search space. Similarly, intuition applies an elimination algorithm that prioritizes the most significant and relevant attributes of a given context while disregarding irrelevant details. This approach enables intuition to effectively manage the challenge of context, much like Expert-AI's algorithms, making it a powerful tool for navigating complex and uncertain situations.

The Brain Is A Pattern Recognition Entity

In recent years, there has been extensive research on the brain's ability to recognize patterns, leading to the hypothesis that the brain is a pattern recognition entity. This hypothesis (Thomas A, 2023) suggests that intuition may be based on an elimination algorithm using combinatorial recognition in nerve cell decision making. Recent advances in understanding the nervous system show that nerve cells communicate with each other through a complex network of connections known as synapses, allowing for complex combinatorial decisions at the axon hillock. The olfactory system (Kaplan BA, 2014) uses combinatorial pattern recognition to identify different odors, allowing the brain to recognize a vast number of odors using a limited number of receptors. The idea behind the hypothesis is that the brain may use a similar mechanism to recognize patterns in other domains, such as social interactions or decision making. The brain creates a database of patterns and uses a process of elimination to match incoming information to the appropriate pattern. This process of elimination is based on combinatorial recognition, allowing the brain to recognize a vast number of patterns using a limited number of neurons. The paper provides evidence from research results of the olfactory system, which uses combinatorial pattern recognition, to support the argument that intuition is a pattern recognition algorithm. The paper's perspective is that consciousness can be conceived as the pattern recognition signals generated by the brain, in contrast to some scientific views that view consciousness as an inscrutable concept. (Hunter P. 2006) According to this view, intuition can be considered a pattern recognition algorithm, which presents the mind as an entity that recognizes patterns. This understanding of consciousness has significant implications for the scientific comprehension of the brain's recognition of patterns through signals. In summary, the overwhelming evidence suggests that intuition follows an elimination algorithm and that the brain is wholly a pattern recognition entity.

Historic View Of Consciousness

One of the earliest interpretations of consciousness was that it is a spiritual or paranormal entity that exists independent of the physical body. This view is still held by some today, although it has largely fallen out of favor in scientific circles. The idea that consciousness is a non-physical entity has been challenged by the observation that brain damage or drugs can alter consciousness. If consciousness were a spiritual entity, it should not be susceptible to such physical changes. The hard problem of consciousness, first described by philosopher David Chalmers, (Chalmers DJ, 2013) is the question of how physical processes in the brain give rise to subjective experience. How can the firing of neurons and the movement of chemicals result in the subjective experience of, say, seeing the color red? This question has confounded philosophers and

neuroscientists alike, and there is no consensus on an answer. One approach to solving the hard problem (Klein C, 2020) is to propose a separation between the mind and body, where consciousness exists outside of the physical world. This view has been put forth by philosophers such as René Descartes and is still held by some today. Others, such as behaviorists, deny the existence of the hard problem altogether, arguing that consciousness is simply a byproduct of physical processes in the brain. Another interpretation of consciousness is panpsychism, (Lamme VAF, 2018) the idea that all things, including inanimate objects, have some level of consciousness. This view is gaining popularity in some scientific circles, with proponents arguing that consciousness is an inherent property of matter, much like mass or charge. In recent years, some neuroscientists have proposed that consciousness is a pattern recognition output of the brain. This view suggests that the brain processes information in a way that leads to the subjective experience of consciousness. In conclusion, consciousness is a complex and multifaceted concept that has been interpreted in a variety of ways throughout history. Philosophers have proposed a separation between the mind and body, denied the existence of the hard problem, and even suggested that all things are conscious. This paper presents a novel perspective on consciousness that suggests that with the ongoing evolution of scientific understanding of the brain and its processes, fresh interpretations of consciousness may arise, leading to the resolution of the long-standing hard problem.

Consciousness is a Complex Exchange of Brain Signals

Consciousness is often thought of as the highest form of awareness, encompassing our thoughts, actions, and self-awareness. However, recent scientific findings suggest that these aspects of consciousness are merely created by the flow of electrical impulses through nerve channels in the brain. Francis Crick, a renowned scientist, posited that the claustrum, (Goll Y, 2015) a thin layer of gray matter in the brain, could be responsible for enabling consciousness. The claustrum is thought to coordinate information from various sensory domains, allowing for the integrated perception of multiple objects and events, rather than isolated attributes. When the claustrum is deactivated, patients lose consciousness. Conscious awareness receives observation signals from the brain, such as the decision-making process of the motor system, which can act before conscious awareness is even aware of it. This finding is supported by the experiments conducted by Benjamin Libet, (Libet B. 2006) who studied the relationship between conscious will and the brain's activity. Libet found that unconscious processes in the brain precede conscious decisions. This challenges the view that conscious will is the cause of our actions, suggesting that it is merely an illusion. All these findings suggest that consciousness, including thoughts, actions, and self-awareness, are created by internal patterns of the flow of electrical impulses in the brain. These patterns create a complex network of interactions that enable us to experience the world around us, including our own thoughts and actions. While these findings may challenge traditional views of consciousness, they have opened up new avenues for research and investigation.

In conclusion, recent scientific findings suggest that consciousness, including our thoughts, actions, and self-awareness, are created by the flow of electrical impulses through nerve channels in the brain. The claustrum is thought to coordinate information from various sensory domains, enabling the integrated perception of multiple objects and events. Additionally, research has shown that unconscious processes in the brain precede conscious decisions, challenging the view that conscious will is the cause of our actions. These findings open up new avenues for understanding the workings of the brain and the complex mechanisms that create our conscious experience.

Conclusion

This paper presents a new perspective on consciousness as a pattern recognition signal of the brain. The paper argues that the similarity of the expert system developed by the author to human intuition carries compelling statistical evidence of intuitive resemblance. The paper suggests that the brain applies the intuition algorithm on combinatorial codes, where individual neurons in the brain represent a specific combination of features or concepts, rather than just one specific feature or concept. This framework proposes that consciousness arises from the integration of pattern recognition signals across various regions of the brain, which allows for the generation of coherent perceptual experiences and the ability to make flexible and adaptive decisions. The paper draws on insights from neuroscience, psychology, and computer science to present a new perspective on consciousness as a pattern recognition signal.

Implications

The implications of this new perspective on consciousness as a pattern recognition signal are significant for both scientific research and practical applications. The paper provides a new framework for understanding the nature of consciousness, which may lead to new avenues of research in neuroscience, psychology, and artificial intelligence. The paper suggests that the integration of pattern recognition signals across various regions of the brain plays a crucial role in the generation of coherent perceptual experiences, which has implications for the understanding of mental disorders, such as schizophrenia and autism. The paper also suggests that the expert system developed by the author, which shows a strong resemblance to human intuition, has potential practical applications in the fields of medicine, engineering, and finance, where pattern recognition is critical for decision-making. Overall, this new perspective on consciousness as a pattern recognition signal has broad implications for both scientific research and practical applications.

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